

Towards a Critical Approach in Applied Ethnomusicology: Negotiating Power, Engagement and Cultural Sustainability in the Heritage Celebrations, Penang, Malaysia

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Abstract. Recent debates in applied ethnomusicology and critical heritage studies illustrate that music, the performing arts and other forms of intangible cultural heritage (ICH) are socially created and have political dimensions (Hemetek et al, 2019). As such, ICH is continually being appropriated by hegemonic structures of power such as nation states, universities, business corporations and local associations led by elites who intervene in heritage making following their own agendas. Yet, as “living heritage embodied in people” (UNESCO, 2003), ICH forms the foundation of the evolving cultural identities of local communities. As a consequence, conflicts and contestations occur between different groups over the ownership of ICH and how art forms are to be represented and conserved (Langfield et al 2016, Hall 1997). Following this discourse, sustaining ICH on their own terms becomes a human right of the local communities (Schippers and Grant 2016). Nevertheless, community engagement is a challenging task. Ethnomusicologists and heritage practitioners have begun to engage in reflexivity regarding their roles as researchers and to make critical shifts in their approaches in research, such as including tradition bearers as equal collaborative partners in and producers of knowledge (Titon, 2015; Araujo et al, 2006). This paper continues the dialogue as it deliberates the complex intersections between the sustainability of ICH, community engagement and power related issues that affect the custodians and the sustainability of their ICH in George Town, a UNESCO World heritage site based in Penang, Malaysia. I share the bottom-up strategies used to engage the diverse local communities to actively identify, interpret, manage and perform their ICH as well as to pass them to the younger generation through the annual Heritage Celebrations. As there are many stakeholders who have conflicting views over how ICH and the arts are to be presented, researchers and heritage practitioners need to be cautious of simple dichotomies such as hegemonic/resistant, state/community and majority/minority.

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